

Intercomparison of Earth Observation products for hyper-resolution hydrological modelling over Europe

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Abstract.

The increasing frequency and severity of hydrological extremes demand the development of early warning systems and effective adaptation and mitigation strategies. Such systems and strategies require spatially detailed hydrological predictions, mostly provided by hydrological models. However, current state-of-the-art hydrological predictions remain limited in their spatial resolution. A proposed solution is the integration of high-resolution (< 1 km) Earth observation (EO) products in hydrological modelling in order to reach hyper-resolution (approximately 1 km²). Nonetheless, proper use of these data in hydrological modelling requires a comprehensive characterisation of their uncertainties. Here, we evaluate the performance of high-resolution EO products of four hydrological variables (8 precipitation products, 5 snow cover area products, 6 surface soil moisture products, and 6 actual evapotranspiration products) against observational references. Two merged EO precipitation products at 1 km resolution (merged IMERG-SM2A and merged ERA5-IMERG-SM2A) reached correlation coefficients >0.5 with the benchmark reference over most areas and are recommended for hyper-resolution hydrological modelling over Europe. The MODIS (resolution of 250 m) and Sentinel-2/Landsat-8 (resolution of 20 m) snow cover products showed the highest classification accuracy and were selected as best choice for the use of snow cover area products in hyper-resolution hy-

drological modelling. For surface soil moisture, the NSIDC SMAP product at 1 km resolution yielded correlation coefficients
15 >0.6 at most stations and is recommended for hyper-resolution hydrological modelling. Finally, evapotranspiration products
showed similar performances at the selected flux sites (> 0.8), but there may be some advantage by using the MODIS-Terra
(MOD16A2) evapotranspiration product for hyper-resolution hydrological modelling due to its higher spatial resolution (500
m). The assimilation of the proposed high-resolution products in models individually or in combination could lead us to hyper-
resolution hydrological modelling. Still, developing integration workflows is required to overcome difficulties related to scale
20 mismatches and data-gaps.

Copyright statement.

1 Introduction

Climate change and global warming lead to an increase in the occurrence and intensity of hydrological extremes (e.g. droughts
and floods) globally (Seneviratne et al., 2021). Climate change is associated with changes in extreme precipitation patterns,
25 possibly leading to more frequent heavy precipitation episodes and extraordinary high stream flows (Ludwig et al., 2023).
Heavy precipitation episodes, such as those occurring in 2021 over western Europe and in 2024 over eastern Spain, caused
infrastructure damage and widespread societal impact (Mohr et al., 2023). Further, the global temperature increase has con-
tributed to more frequent agricultural droughts via increased evaporative demand, threatening food security and ecosystem
productivity (Markonis et al., 2021; Trnka et al., 2014). For example, a combination of high temperatures and lack of pre-
30 cipitation caused the 2018 drought over Northern and Eastern Europe, and induced multiple crop failures over the continent
(Beillouin et al., 2020). Agricultural droughts can propagate to hydrological droughts via an increase in evapotranspiration
for a prolonged duration, affecting water supplies. This was the case of the 2015 and 2022 droughts that affected river flows,
drinking water supply, energy production and forest fires all over Europe (Laaha et al., 2017; Joint Research Centre et al.,
2022). Droughts can also be a driver of heat events in soil and air via soil moisture feedbacks, seriously affecting the evolution
35 of heat events in Europe (García-García et al., 2023; Hauser et al., 2016). Thus, the current observed trends in the occurrence
and intensity of hydrological extremes demand new adaptive water management policies to mitigate their impacts on society
and ecosystems.

Hydrological and land surface models (HMs/LSMs) can be employed to develop early warning systems (Trnka et al., 2020)
and, in combination with climate scenarios, to develop and optimize effective adaptation and mitigation strategies (Samaniego
40 et al., 2018; Wanders et al., 2019; Imhoff et al., 2024). High spatial and temporal resolutions are required to provide infor-
mation relevant to this task (Bierkens et al., 2015). However, uncertainties in meteorological forcings and the limitations in
the simulation of physical processes at fine spatial scales have prevented important advances in this direction (Samaniego
et al., 2017). Due to the recent advances in deriving high-resolution products of hydrological variables with remote sensing
(RS) technologies (e.g. the products developed in the ESA 4DMED-Hydrology project, Massari et al. (2022)), the integration

45 of high-resolution (defined here, from a hydrologic modeling perspective, as finer than 1 km²) Earth observations (EO) in
physical models have been proposed as a solution to reach hyper-resolution (~1 km²) in hydrological modelling (e.g. Khaki
et al., 2020). Several approaches can be applied for the integration of EO products in hydrological modelling, for example, EO
products are used in the model building (e.g. land use, digital elevation model), as forcing data, for initialising models and in
the calibration and validation process (Silvestro et al., 2015; Thakur et al., 2017; Peña-Arancibia et al., 2016; Demirel et al.,
50 2018).

Different approaches have been employed to reach fine scales in EO products. For example, high-resolution precipitation
products have been produced using clouds and atmosphere information (Top-Down method, Kucera et al., 2013), soil moisture
information (Bottom-Up method, Brocca et al., 2014) and merging both approaches (Ciabatta et al., 2017) as well as based on
SAR data (Marzano et al., 2011). Snow cover data at high-resolution can be obtained from radiance data from MODIS and
55 Landsat, SAR data from Sentinel-1 and multispectral images from Sentinel-2 (e.g. Notarnicola et al., 2013a; Gascoin et al.,
2019; Barrou Dumont et al., 2021). In the case of soil moisture, EO products at high-resolution can be achieved directly from
Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data (e.g. from Sentinel-1 data Balenzano et al., 2021) or by integrating coarse-resolution
data from radiometers or scatterometers with solar-reflective, optical/thermal, or SAR data (e.g. Colliander et al., 2017; Peng
et al., 2021). Evapotranspiration estimates from remote sensing (RS) products always rely on modelling frameworks since
60 surface turbulent fluxes can not be directly measured from space. Thus, high-resolution evapotranspiration products are derived
from the combination of EO retrievals and meteorological products (in-situ measurements or reanalysis) with physical and/or
machine learning based modelling frameworks (McShane et al., 2017; Garcia-Garcia and Peng, 2024; Zhang et al., 2016).
The combination of EO with modeling frameworks has also been explored for the rest of hydrological variables (e.g. for soil
moisture O. and Orth, 2020). Nevertheless, uncertainties arising from the different observations and approaches can reduce
65 the signal-to-noise ratio of the high-resolution products for all variables, affecting the added value of these products at fine
scales. Thus, although there are new datasets of hydrometeorological variables (precipitation, snow cover, soil moisture and
evapotranspiration) derived from remote sensing data at very high-resolution (~1 km), these products are also vulnerable to
uncertainties arising from RS technologies or the downscaling technique.

In order to integrate high-resolution products into HM/LSM simulations via assimilation or calibration schemes, a com-
70 prehensive assessment of high-resolution EO products addressing the needs for reaching hyper-resolution in hydrological
modelling is necessary. The objective of the present study is, therefore, to provide a thorough comparative assessment of high-
resolution EO-based products for hydrological modelling over Europe. Special attention has been paid to the technical features
required for the integration of high-resolution EO products in HM/LSM simulations. Spatial and temporal continuity in the EO
products is desirable for smoothly implementing data assimilation algorithms. Spatial details corresponding to resolutions finer
75 than 1 km are desired to improve the spatial patterns in the model simulations with a spatial resolution of 1 km. RS products
with daily or sub-daily re-visiting time are expected to reach the best added value in assimilation schemes. Thus, considering
these requirements and the hydrological relevance of environmental variables, high-resolution EO products of precipitation
(P), snow cover area (SCA), surface soil moisture (SSM), and evapotranspiration (ET) have been selected for this intercom-
parison. Other variables, such as ground water or snow water equivalent, could also improve hydrological modelling, but the

80 limited penetration depth of remote sensing products at high resolution (Li et al., 2021) and uncertainties associated with the estimates of snow water equivalent (Dozier et al., 2016) prevent us to include these variables in the analysis. Based on the intercomparison results, some recommendations are provided for the future use of EO products in hyper-resolution hydrological modelling.

2 Data and Methods

85 The evaluation of EO products for three of the four hydrological variables (precipitation, surface soil moisture and evapotranspiration) uses similar methods and metrics. A different methodology is applied for the evaluation of snow products due to the binary nature of SCA datasets. The domain for the intercomparison is Europe for P, SSM and ET, and the Alps mountain range for the SCA products.

The selected evaluation metrics for the P, SSM and ET intercomparisons against station observations are widely used in literature: temporal mean bias, temporal root mean square error (RMSE), and temporal Pearson's correlation coefficients (R). The comparison between EO products and in-situ datasets is performed at the highest possible temporal resolution according to the EO datasets. Thus, daily averages are computed for P and SSM, but estimates with an 8-day resolution are employed to evaluate ET due to data availability of some of the used ET products. The conversion of sub-daily data from EO products and observations to daily estimates was done, calculating daily averages from sub-daily time series only on days with at least 80% of values in a day, that is more than 20 measurements per day in hourly data as in e.g. García-García et al. (2019). The temporal series of each EO product are compared against the benchmark product of each variable, selecting the closest pixel of each EO product to the location of the observational data. The intercomparison includes only observational locations with all EO products showing a grid point within a certain radius of the observation location/station. The size of the radius depends on the resolution of the EO products selected for each variable and the footprint of the benchmark dataset.

100 2.1 Precipitation

In the intercomparison of the precipitation datasets, seven precipitation products derived from remote sensing data, reanalysis and in-situ observations are compared (Table 1). The selection of products includes datasets at different spatial resolutions to test the advantage of the high-resolution products. The product selection includes three coarse-resolution EO products widely used in the literature (CHIRPS, IMERG-LR and SM2RAIN-ASCAT). CHIRPS is based on data from thermal infrared sensors combined with the globally gridded satellite from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) (Funk et al., 2014). IMERG-LR is produced by the Integrated Multi-satellitE Retrievals for GPM (IMERG) algorithm with data from the GPM mission (Huffman et al., 2015). The SM2RAIN-ASCAT product is based on the SM2RAIN algorithm (Brocca et al., 2019) using SSM observations from the ASCAT product (Wagner et al., 2013). These three coarse resolution EO products are compared with two high-resolution datasets (1 km) produced from the downscaling and combination of SM2RAIN and IMERG-LR precipitation estimates (Merged IMERG-SM2A) and from the combination of the same two products with ERA5 estimates (Merged ERA5-IMERG-SM2A) using a triple collocation technique (more information about the merging approach

Product	Years	Temp. Res.	Cov.	Spat. Res. (km)	Source	Reference
Precipitation						
CHIRPS	1981–2022	1d	50S–50N	5	EO	Funk et al. (2014)
IMERG-LR	2000–2022	0.5h	Global	10	EO	Huffman et al. (2015)
SM2RAIN-ASCAT	2007–2022	d	Global	12.5	EO	Brocca et al. (2019)
Merged IMERG-SM2A	2007–2022	1d	Global	1	EO	Filippucci et al. (2025)
Merged ERA5-IMERG-SM2A	2007–2022	1d	Global	1	EO+Reanalysis	Filippucci et al. (2025)
EMO	1990–2022	6h	Europe	1.5	Gridded	Gomes et al. (2020)
ERA5	1940–present	1h	Global	25	Reanalysis	Muñoz Sabater et al. (2021)
Snow cover area						
MODIS SCA	2002–present	1d	Global	0.25	EO	Notarnicola et al. (2013a, b)
Sentinel-2/Landsat-8 SCA	2016–present / 2013–2021	5d/8d	Europe	0.02/0.03	EO	Gascoin et al. (2019)
Sentinel-2 FSC	2016–present	5d	Europe	0.02	EO	Barrou Dumont et al. (2021)
Sentinel GFSC	2016–present	1d	Europe	0.06	EO	Barrou Dumont et al. (2021)
Sentinel-1 HS	2017–2019	1d	Europe	0.5	EO	Lievens et al. (2019, 2022)
Surface soil moisture						
NSIDC SMAP 1km	2015–2022	1d	Global	1	EO	Lakshmi and Fang. (2023)
BEC SMOS L4	2010–2022	1–3d	Europe	1	EO	Piles et al. (2014)
CGLS SWI	2015–present	1d	Europe	1	EO	Bauer-Marschallinger et al. (2018)
CGLS SSM	2015–present	3–8d	Europe	1	EO	Bauer-Marschallinger et al. (2019)
UFZ-S1	2016–2022	3–8d	Global	1	EO	Fan et al. (2024)
ESACCISM 1km	2008–2020	1d	Europe	1	EO	Himmer et al. (2024)
Evapotranspiration						
ALEXI	2001–2021	1d	Global	5	EO+Reanalysis	Hain and Anderson (2017)
AVHRR	1982–2018	8d	Global	5	EO+Reanalysis	Yao et al. (2014)
GLEAM	2003–2021	1d	Global	25	EO+Reanalysis	Martens et al. (2017)
HOLAPS	2001–2020	0.5h	Europe	5	EO+Reanalysis	Garcia-Garcia and Peng (2024)
MODIS-Aqua	2002–2021	8d	Global	0.5	EO+Reanalysis	Running et al. (2021a)
MODIS-Terra	2000–2021	8d	Global	0.5	EO+Reanalysis	Running et al. (2021b)

Table 1. Overview of the selected products.

in Filippucci et al., 2025). All these EO-based products are also compared with estimates from the ERA5 Land reanalysis (Muñoz Sabater et al., 2021) and the EMO-1 gridded meteorological dataset (Gomes et al., 2020).

Another gridded observational dataset for precipitation is employed as a benchmark in the evaluation, the E-OBS v25.0e
115 dataset. The E-OBS dataset is produced based on in-situ observations from European meteorological stations. The gridded
product has a final resolution of 10 km with daily estimates of accumulated precipitation rates from 1950–2021 (Cornes et al.,
2018). The E-OBS dataset was selected as a benchmark due to the integration of data from more than 22600 stations in the
dataset and its good performance reported in the literature (e.g. Bandhauer et al., 2022). Performance metrics were calculated
against E-OBS reference by resampling all the EO products to the E-OBS grid.

120 **2.2 Snow**

The evaluation of low and medium resolution snow cover area EO products have been already reported in the literature (Met-
sämäki et al., 2016, 2017). Therefore, only high-resolution and one medium resolution products are selected for this intercom-
parison (Table 1). These products include the medium resolution MODIS product (Notarnicola et al., 2013a, b) provided by
Eurac Research (<https://edp-portal.eurac.edu/discovery/52c3684a-7964-11ee-9a8e-47abc4958022>), one product derived from
125 Sentinel-2 and Landsat-8 images (Gascoin et al., 2019) and provided by Theia (<https://www.theia-land.fr/en/product/snow/>),
the fractional snow cover (FSC) product based on Sentinel-2 images provided by the Copernicus Land Monitoring Ser-
vice (<https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/snow/fractional-snow-cover>), the gap-filled fractional snow cover product (GFSC)
based on Sentinel-1 wet snow maps and snow cover extent from Sentinel-2 (Barrou Dumont et al., 2021) and provided by the
Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (<https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/snow/high-resolution-gap-filled-fractional-snow-cover>),
130 and a snow depth (HS) product derived from Sentinel-1 images (Lievens et al., 2019, 2022) in the context of the C-SNOW
project (<https://ees.kuleuven.be/project/c-snow>). In-situ measurements collected over Europe (Matiu et al., 2021) are employed
as benchmark in the SCA intercomparison. This observational dataset includes data from more than 2000 meteorological sta-
tions over the Alps during 1971–2019.

All snow EO products are transformed to binary SCA maps following the SKYE approach for the validation of snow products
135 against in situ measurements proposed in the SnowPEX project (Metsämäki et al., 2016, 2017; Ripper et al., 2019). For the
transformation of the snow datasets to binary SCA maps, the thresholds of > 0 cm and > 2 cm are considered for the HS
product and in-situ data, and a threshold of $> 25\%$ is employed for FSC and GFSC estimates. Each pixel in the SCA maps is
compared with the in-situ data contained in that pixel. The evaluation was performed over the Alps during the winters 2017–
2018 and 2018–2019 due to data availability. The metrics suggested by Ripper et al. (2019), evaluated from a contingency
140 matrix, will be employed: (i) recall, defined as the ability to identify true snow; (ii) precision, to measure how much classified
snow is actually snow; (iii) false positive rate (FPR), to identify untrue snow classification; (iv) accuracy, defined as the overall
classification accuracy; (v) critical success index (CSI), i.e., false snow omissions/false snow commissions; and (vi) F-score,
as a measure of accuracy mixing Recall and Precision.

2.3 Soil moisture

145 The six selected SSM products provide surface soil moisture (0–5 cm) estimates at 1 km resolution based on Sentinel-1 SAR
data (CGLS SSM and UFZ-S1) or from the disaggregation of coarse resolution products (Table 1). NSIDC SMAP is derived

from the combination of L-band SMAP and surface temperature and NDVI information from MODIS (Fang et al., 2022). BEC SMOS L4 is produced based on SMOS L3 v4.0, surface temperature from the ERA5Land reanalysis and NDVI from MODIS (Pablos et al., 2022). CGLS SWI is produced from the combination of ASCAT data and Sentinel-1 (Bauer-Marschallinger et al., 2018). ESA CCI SM 1km is downscaled from the ESACCISM v8.1 COMBINED data at the original resolution (~ 25 km) Dorigo et al. (2017); Gruber et al. (2019), using a combination of dynamic variables such as NDVI and static variables like topography, soil properties or land cover (Himmer et al., 2024).

Soil moisture in-situ observations from the International Soil Moisture Network (ISMN) Dorigo et al. (2013a, 2021) are employed as a benchmark in the SSM evaluation. This database contain in-situ measurements from several networks (Musial et al., 2016; Zreda et al., 2008, 2012; Al-Yaari et al., 2018; Wigneron et al., 2018; Xaver et al., 2020; Zappa et al., 2019, 2020; Blöschl et al., 2016; Vreugdenhil et al., 2013; Bircher et al., 2012; Jensen and Refsgaard, 2018; Flammini et al., 2018a, b; Morbidelli et al., 2011, 2014, 2017; Biddoccu et al., 2016; Capello et al., 2019a; Raffelli et al., 2017; Alday et al., 2020; Mattar et al., 2016, 2014; Smith et al., 2012; Young et al., 2008; González-Zamora et al., 2019; Calvet et al., 2016; Albergel et al., 2008; Calvet et al., 2007; Capello et al., 2019b; Darouich et al., 2022; Marczewski et al., 2010; Zacharias et al., 2011; Bogena et al., 2018, 2012; Bogena, 2016; Schlenz et al., 2012; Loew et al., 2009; Brocca et al., 2011, 2008, 2009; Bell et al., 2013; Fuchsberger et al., 2021; Kirchengast et al., 2014; Petropoulos and McCalmont, 2017). The soil moisture data measured in the upper 10 cm of the soil were employed in the analysis while masking for spurious observations using the flags provided (Dorigo et al., 2013b). Due to the large variability in the value ranges of the soil moisture products, the unbiased RMSE and R were employed as metrics in the SSM benchmarking.

All products were processed considering the recommendation of Gruber et al. (2020). Thus, time series of daily measurements were extracted for each product at the closest pixel to each station, when all products have a grid point in a 2.5 km radius of the station. Temporal series from all EO products were also re-scaled, matching the mean and standard deviation against that of the in-situ measurements to avoid discrepancies arising from different units and to account for the spatial scale mismatch of EO estimates.

2.4 Evapotranspiration

Six different EO evapotranspiration products have been selected for the intercomparison (Table 1). The products have been chosen based on their spatial and temporal coverage, resolution, and use in the literature. Therefore, the Global Land Evaporation Amsterdam Model (GLEAM) estimates were selected despite its coarse resolution due to its reported good performance (Martens et al., 2017). Three products with medium resolution were also included in the comparison (ALEXI, AVHRR and HO-LAPS), all of them derived from remote sensing products applying different approaches (Hain and Anderson, 2017; Yao et al., 2014; Garcia-Garcia and Peng, 2024). Finally, the MODIS-Aqua and MODIS-Terra are included in the comparison despite their coarse temporal resolution (8-days) to evaluate the added value of high spatial resolution (500 m) EO evapotranspiration products.

As a reference dataset, the eddy covariance measurements from the ICOS network (Warm Winter 2020 Team and ICOS Ecosystem Thematic Centre, 2022) have been employed to evaluate EO products. The ICOS dataset includes latent heat flux

measurements at 73 sites over Europe. The eddy covariance reference dataset was filtered by the domain of all products, resulting in 37 usable sites over different land cover types and ecosystems. We acknowledge that some of these sites do not provide observations that are representative at the model pixel scale. Thus, we rely on the aggregate statistics over the 32 sites, where all ET products contain data, to provide information on relative model performance. The daily gap-filled series of latent
185 heat flux at each site were converted to evapotranspiration (mm). Due to the different temporal resolutions of the selected EO products, the products were homogenized by aggregating the daily data to the 8-day time step to match the temporal resolution of MODIS. In addition to the metrics suggested for the common evaluation (bias, RMSE and R), the mean absolute error was included in the ET experiment as a measure of the absolute errors in the products.

3 Results

190 The intercomparison results are organized by variable to identify the EO products with higher potential for hyper-resolution modelling.

3.1 Precipitation

The RMSE metrics of all precipitation products against the E-OBS product show large errors over the coastal areas of the Mediterranean Sea and the North Sea (Fig. 1). The IMERG-LR (10 km resolution) is the product reaching the worst performance of RMSE against the observational gridded product. Despite the coarser resolution of the SM2RAIN-ASCAT product
195 (12.5 km), the RMSE of this product against the benchmark dataset is lower over the whole domain, probably because a monthly BIAS correction against ERA5 rainfall data is included in the product generation. However, SM2RAIN-ASCAT exhibits data gaps across many northern latitudes regions due to the inability to obtain SM data from EO under frozen conditions. Additionally, data for coastal areas were masked by the SM provider due to an error, which is expected to be resolved in a
200 future version of the dataset, leading to further gaps and low performance near the coasts for SM2RAIN-ASCAT. The CHIRPS product (5 km) reaches similar RMSE metrics to the SM2RAIN-ASCAT product, showing no advantage of the finer spatial resolutions when using E-OBS (10 km) as reference (Fig. 1). In terms of RMSE, the merging algorithm employed to combine the IMERG-LR and SM2RAIN-ASCAT products (Merged IMERG-SM2A, 1 km) shows performance that falls between that of individual IMERG-LR and SM2RAIN-ASCAT products, due to the limitations of the former. However, the merged product
205 which includes information from the ERA5 reanalysis (Merged ERA5-IMERG-SM2A) improves a lot, showing RMSE < 4 mm in most of the domain. This is due to the good performance of the ERA5 products in comparison with the E-OBS product (Fig. 1). The evaluation of the EMO product also shows very low RMSE values over most of the domain, probably because of the use of the same in-situ data in the production of the E-OBS and EMO datasets.

Similar results are obtained from the analysis of the results in terms of Pearson's Correlation (Fig. 2), which also indicates
210 better performances of the products that integrate in-situ/reanalysis data in comparison with pure remote sensing products, regardless of the product's spatial resolution (Fig. 2). In general, the Pearson's correlation of IMERG-LR against E-OBS is greater than that of SM2RAIN-ASCAT, primarily due to its superior performance at high latitudes. CHIRP performance are

Figure 1. Maps and boxplots of daily root mean square error of the precipitation products against the E-OBS dataset over Europe for the period 2007-2022.

similar to those of SM2RAIN-ASCAT; however, the analysis is somewhat biased by the fact that no data from CHIRP is available above 50°N (where SM2RAIN-ASCAT performs the worst), suggesting that the latter’s overall performance may appear slightly better. For this performance index, merging the signals from IMERG and SM2RAIN-ASCAT outperforms all individual satellite products, demonstrating that the merging procedure effectively leverages the strengths of both approaches. It should be finally noticed that all the products, from EO, reanalysis or gauge, fails in reproducing the precipitation over east Europe. In this area, very few rain-gauges are available and EMO, ERA5 and E-OBS disagree the most. The high spatial resolution analysis by Filippucci et al. (2025) indicates that, in this region, EO information can infer actual precipitation data with greater accuracy than the benchmark datasets, as the limited number of observed data points does not constrain it.

Figure 2. Maps and boxplots of daily Pearson's correlation coefficients of the precipitation products against the E-OBS dataset over Europe for the period 2007-2022.

The analysis of BIAS errors in EO products further confirms the above results (Fig. 3). IMERG-LR exhibits the highest BIAS, followed by the merged IMERG-SM2A, merged ERA5-IMERG-SM2A, ERA5 and then the other two pure satellite products, CHIRP and SM2RAIN-ASCAT. Notably, all the EO-based products tend to underestimate precipitation in topographically complex areas (such as the Alps, Apennines, Pyrenees, Pontic Mountains, and Taurus Mountains) and in isolated regions (including northern Britain, southwest Ireland, and Scandinavia). However, the absence of gauge stations in these areas raises questions about the accuracy of the E-OBS product as a reference. Similarly, EMO bias against E-OBS is the lowest, owing to the use of the same observed data. Discrepancies arise in some regions, such as northern regions, central and southern Italy, and Western Europe.

Figure 3. Maps and boxplots of daily mean bias in the precipitation products against the E-OBS dataset over Europe for the period 2007-2022.

To sum up, pure RS products show good capacity in estimating precipitation when merging the two typical approaches (Bottom-Up and Top-Down). Pure EO products could benefit from the combination with reanalysis information particularly in areas with large density of in-situ observations integrated in the reanalysis. However, EO products could be key in areas with low density of observations. The advantages of the high spatial resolution obtained from the downscaling of the original EO data were not addressed in this paper, being already described in Filippucci et al. (2025). The performance of all products integrating gauge observations was also shown to be better against the E-OBS product, but this comparison could be biased due to the integration of observations from the same stations in E-OBS and EMO products. Therefore, we recommend the use of the two merged products at 1 km resolution for hyper-resolution hydrological modelling over Europe and more specifically of the pure satellite merged products in regions with limited observed data. Ideally, the added value of the use of the two

merged products in hydrological modelling should be compared against independent observations, such as evapotranspiration or streamflow data.

240 3.2 Snow

Figure 4. Evaluation metrics of snow cover area products against in-situ measurements in the Alps for the winters from 2017 to 2019, considering a threshold of 25% for fractional snow cover (FSC) and gap-filled fractional snow cover (GFSC) products and a) snow depth (HS) > 0 cm, b) HS > 2 cm.

The comparison of the EO product performance for reproducing the in-situ observations of snow leads to a similar conclusion using a threshold of > 0 cm or > 2 cm for the translation of snow estimates to binary data (Fig. 4). All products show a high recall value (> 0.8), indicating that all products can identify snow accurately. The highest recall values are shown by the Sentinel-1 HS (KU Leuven), MODIS SCA (Eurac Research) and Sentinel-2/Landsat-8 SCA (Theia) products (Fig. 4). The false positive ratio is, however, higher for the Sentinel-1 HS (C-SNOW) product. The precision of most products is also very good (> 0.95), except for the Sentinel-1 HS (KU Leuven) product (>0.8), probably because of the false snow cases reported in this product. Regarding the accuracy, false snow commission and F-score, the MODIS SCA (Eurac Research) and Sentinel-2/Landsat-8 SCA (Theia) show the highest values among all products (Fig. 4). The results show a slight advantage of the gap-filled product due to the dates selected for the multi-product comparison and the data availability of other products (Fig. 4). A detailed description of the methodology followed for the intercomparison of SCA products and a comprehensive analysis of the results is reported in Di Paolo et al. (2025).

Based on the results shown in Figure 4 and the characteristics of each of the snow products presented in Table 1, we recommend the use of the MODIS and Sentinel-2/Landsat-8 SCA datasets provided by Eurac Research and Theia, respectively, for hyper-resolution hydrological modelling. When comparing the products features, the main difference between the two products is that MODIS SCA maps are retrieved daily, whereas Theia SCA maps have a higher resolution. Although the resolution of the MODIS is not the highest, it is in the order of snow model resolutions (Endrizzi et al., 2014; Avanzi et al.,

2023) and, depending on the case, the daily revisit time of the product could increase the impact of assimilating the product in hydrological models in comparison with other products with higher spatial resolution.

3.3 Soil moisture

260 The unbiased RMSE (ubRMSE) and R for the high-resolution SSM estimates against the point reference locations are shown in Figures 5, 6. The ubRMSE follows similar patterns for all products, with the lowest overall ubRMSE values against the ground networks of Romania, Norway, and Spain. The in situ network in the Twente region (NL) displays high uncertainties at all stations. In the densely instrumented UK area, strong spatial gradients in the ubRMSE are observed for all satellite products. The CGLS SSM, UFZ-S1, and SMOS BEC L2 products show the highest uncertainties in this region.

265 The R patterns follow closely the ones observed for the ubRMSE. Strong correlations are observed in the REMEDHUS (western Spain) and HOBE (Denmark) networks, particularly for the disaggregated products. Null and weak correlations occur across the domain for the purely Sentinel-1 based UFZ-S1 and CGLS SSM products, often between the two (e.g., SMOSMANIA (FR) and COSMOS-UK networks).

Figure 5. Maps of daily unbiased root mean square error of the surface soil moisture products against in-situ measurements from the ISMN dataset over Europe for the period 2016–2020.

Figure 6. Maps of daily Pearson's correlation coefficients of the surface soil moisture products against in-situ measurements from the ISMN dataset over Europe for the period 2016-2020.

Figure 7 summarizes the scores distributions of the products. The high-resolution soil moisture bulk time series show median 270 ubRMSE values approximately in the $0.06 - 0.08$ (m^3/m^3) range. The products with the lowest error are (in order of increasing error) the disaggregated ESACCISM, SMAP, and CGLS SWI products. The first two are produced from the disaggregation of coarse resolution data using NDVI data, the latter from the fusion of Sentinel-1 data (high-resolution and low revisit frequency) with ASCAT scatterometer data (high revisit frequency and 25 km resolution).

The same product ranking is observed in terms of temporal R as for the unbiased RMSE. The three best-performing products 275 show average correlation coefficients above 0.5 against in situ measurements, which denote a good overall agreement. The downscaled SMOS and the two Sentinel-1-based datasets are less correlated (~ 0.4), with the UFZ-S1 product showing the largest disagreement with the reference data.

All high-resolution EO products derived from disaggregated methods show a good performance in reproducing surface soil 280 moisture values from in-situ stations. The advantages of the high-resolution products were, however, not tested in this analysis in comparison with coarser products. Nevertheless, the SSM products' high-resolution spatial pattern could help improve the spatial information of hydrological simulations. Thus, based on the metrics of each of the disaggregated SSM products and

Figure 7. Boxplots of daily root mean square error and Pearson’s correlation coefficients between the surface soil moisture products and in-situ measurements from the ISMN dataset over Europe for the period 2016-2020. The grey boxplots indicate the low and high 95% confidence intervals bounds.

their specifications, we recommend using the NSIDC SMAP product to test the added value of high-resolution SSM products in hyper-resolution hydrological modelling.

3.4 Evapotranspiration

285 The intercomparison of the EO evapotranspiration estimates compares the performance of products with different spatial resolutions (0.5 km, 5 km and 25 km) against eddy covariance measurements. The correlation values of the time series extracted from EO products at each eddy covariance site are consistent among datasets, showing no significant spatial pattern in the explained variability (Fig. 8). All products show a good correlation with observations over central Europe and low R values in southern latitudes. This low correlation in southern Spain and the southwestern shore of Italy is most likely caused by the

290 low representativeness of particular sites for larger grid sizes due to complex topography (southern Spain - mountains) and proximity to the sea (southwestern shore of Italy). A few stations in central Europe also show low correlation values (~0.5) for most EO products. This might be associated with the eddy covariance technique’s footprint, typically covering hundreds to thousands of square meters, while the finest resolution of the EO ET product is 500 m.

Figure 9 summarizes the product’s performance across stations using four different metrics (RMSE, bias, MAE and R). To

295 summarize the statistical evaluation - RMSE values of all products indicate a similar performance of all products (Fig. 9), which show comparable medians of RMSE ranging between 0.3 and 0.4, with the highest median but lowest spread of RMSE reached by the GLEAM product. In terms of mean bias, all products show similar errors regardless of the product resolutions, perhaps with the HOLAPS product (5 km) reaching slightly lower values. The medians of Pearson’s correlation coefficients for

Figure 8. Maps of Pearson's correlation coefficients (R) of the evapotranspiration products against measurements at eddy covariance towers over Europe for the period 2003-2020.

all products range between 0.8-0.9. The two high-resolution products provided by MODIS show very similar metrics since the same methods produce them. The results shown in Figures 8 and 9 do not indicate a significant advantage of high-resolution products compared to coarse-resolution EO products. However, a more extensive analysis will be required to assess relative model performance over different landcover types relevant to the hydrologic modeling application of interest. For example, several of these models may not capture the elevated ET encountered in areas of extensive irrigation. A more detailed analysis of evapotranspiration products, supplemented with an ensemble mean of the products and evaluations across different periods of the year can be seen in Orság et al. (2025).

Based on these results and the product characteristics included in Table 1, we can not recommend an individual ET product based merely on the product performances against eddy covariance measurements. Nevertheless, we see advantages in the use of the high-resolution product MODIS-TERRA for the assimilation of ET in hyper-resolution hydrological modelling in order to improve the spatial pattern of the simulation. However, the low data frequency of MODIS (8 days) could reduce the

Figure 9. Boxplots of selected statistical metrics (RMSE, mean bias - MBE, mean absolute error - MAE and Pearson's correlation coefficients) for the evapotranspiration products against measurements at 32 eddy covariance towers for the period 2003–2020.

310 effect of the assimilation process on the hydrological simulation, and other products with similar performance and intermediate resolution (5 km), such as ALEXI, AVHRR or HOLAPS, could be valuable to constrained hydrological modelling based on observational products. The comparison ET products with water balance estimates from streamflow and precipitation measurements could also help to understand the differences between ET products and their implications for hydrological modelling.

4 Discussion

315 Choosing an observational dataset as a benchmark reference is always challenging, since every dataset or observational method may contain or lead to uncertainties. Thus, the intercomparison of all EO products presented here, depends on the uncertainties and limitations of the observational reference selected for each variable. In the evaluation of results of precipitation products, a gridded product with large representation of in-situ measurements (E-OBS) was selected as reference. In areas with low density of observational evidence (e.g. western Europe), satellite estimates may lead to a more accurate representation of precipitation
 320 in the area than the benchmark reference. In the case of evapotranspiration, the common benchmark dataset are measurements from eddy covariance towers (Garcia-Garcia and Peng, 2024). However, the scarcity of observations in comparison with other in-situ measurements and the small footprint of the eddy covariance towers in comparison with ET RS products also limit the investigation of the added value from high-resolution in ET products. The conservation of energy can also be an issue in the use of original measurements at eddy towers. Nevertheless, the use of the reference datasets selected for this study have been
 325 widely supported by the literature. Therefore, our analysis is still valuable for addressing the hyper-resolution problem.

Based on the intercomparison results, one or several high-resolution EO products have been recommended for future testing in hydrological modelling. Comparing R values among hydrological variables ($P \sim 0.75$ in Fig. 2, $SSM \sim 0.6$ in Fig. 7 and $ET \sim 0.85$ in Fig. 9), better correlation values are shown for precipitation and evapotranspiration. However, the different

nature of the benchmarking dataset employed for each benchmarking experiment, demands caution in comparing the products
330 performances. Therefore, other factors, such as spatial and temporal resolutions, should be considered for prioritizing the
assimilation of hydrometeorological variables in hyper-resolution hydrological modelling. Considering this, high-resolution
precipitation datasets could greatly impact hydrological simulations. This is expected due to the involvement of precipitation in
estimating other variables such as soil moisture and evapotranspiration. Additionally, the use of precipitation, usually as forcing
in modelling experiments, simplify its implementation within modelling workflows. Thus, in the case of limited computational
335 resources, we would prioritize the test of the proposed high-resolution precipitation dataset.

We have focused this analysis on four common hydrometeorological variables (precipitation, snow cover area, surface soil
moisture and evapotranspiration). But other variables obtained from the combination of modelling approaches and remote
sensing data could also present several advantages. For example, snow depth or snow water equivalent products are more rele-
vant for hydrological modelling than snow cover area in some models. Root zone soil moisture estimates and terrestrial water
340 anomalies could also improve the water balance of hydrological models. But product uncertainties and the coarse resolution of
ground water estimates limit their current use for hyper-resolution simulations. The integration of other EO products describing
lakes/reservoirs (area, water level or volume) has also a lot of interest for hyper-resolution simulations. But these products are
out of the scope of the current study.

The combination of multiple high-resolution EO products in modelling experiments could also lead to advances in hydro-
345 logical modelling by improving, for example, the simulation of ET and SSM and, therefore, the entire soil hydrology. Thus, the
combination of several EO products should be tested. For example, using the precipitation product together with the assimila-
tion of the suggested soil moisture or evapotranspiration product could improve the representation of floods and droughts within
modelling schemes. The assimilation of ET or SSM should, however, be implemented with caution since the assimilation of
variables could affect the water balance closure of the model. Similarly, the combination of several EO products of the same
350 variable may help to expand the period or domain with available data for model assimilation, but the prior homogenization of
EO products could be a challenge.

There are difficulties associated with the integration of EO products and hydrological modeling at hyper-resolution. For
example, there could be some mismatch between the spatial domain in EO data and in the model (e.g. EO SSM products are
only representative of the first few cm of the soil, whereas models often consider the first 30 cm as a single layer). The use
355 of models in the production of satellite-based ET products could threaten the use of ET estimates as independent reference
for hydrological modelling. And missing values in the EO data due to clouds or satellite coverage could complicate their
integration in spatial and temporal continuous tools like models. Intermediate steps in the EO integration workflows could be
required, for example, to extrapolate the domain or fill data gaps. Data-driven approaches, such as those based on machine
learning algorithms could help to extract the maximum information from EO datasets and bridge scale gaps (Oswald et al.,
360 2024).

Overall, the proposed high-resolution products for each of the hydrometeorological variables selected in this study could
improve the performance of hyper-resolution modelling, but depending on the research question that should be addressed, pri-
ority should be given to different products or the combination of them. It is important to notice that uncertainties in modelling

frameworks could also hide the benefits of high-resolution EO products. To prevent this from happening, collaborative efforts
365 among the modelling community are required to test the same EO products and similar protocols within different models. Col-
laboration with the remote sensing community is also desired in order to ensure the correct interpretation of the EO estimates
and improve the integration workflows. This could be relevant, for example, for taking into account EO product uncertainty
estimates, which are provided alongside the products, in the assimilation of these products into hydrological models. This could
also help to finally determine the benefits of high-resolution EO products for hyper-resolution hydrological modelling.

370 **5 Conclusions**

The intercomparison of EO products for four hydrometeorological variables (precipitation, snow cover area, surface soil mois-
ture and evapotranspiration), focusing on high-resolution products, have yielded recommendations for each variable to be
employed in hydrological modeling applications. The two merged precipitation products at 1 km resolution (merged IMERG-
SM2A and Merged ERA5-IMERG-SM2A) are recommended for hyper-resolution hydrological modelling over Europe. These
375 two EO-based precipitation datasets are recommended to compare their performances and evaluate whether the pure EO prod-
uct (merged IMERG-SM2A) could lead to a more accurate simulation over areas with low density of observational data than
gridded products like ERA5, EMO and E-OBS. Regarding snow cover maps, the MODIS (resolution of 250 m) and Sentinel-
2/Landsat-8 (resolution of 200 m) products are recommended to define snow extension in hydrological simulations. For surface
soil moisture, the NSIDC SMAP product at 1 km resolution is recommended for testing the added value of high-resolution SSM
380 products. And finally, while the RS ET models showed similar performance at the sampled flux tower sites, the higher resolu-
tion of the MODIS ET product may be of benefit for the assimilation of ET in models. However, further analysis is required
to assess how well these remotely sensed products capture response to the hydrologic extremes that the assimilation is geared
toward tackling. Thus, although some challenges should be addressed in the following years to tackle the correct integration of
EO products in hydrological simulations, the spatial details obtained from high-resolution EO data could be the key to finally
385 reach hyper-resolution in hydrological modelling.

Data availability. The EO data products are directly or via intermediate links available in the open science catalog of the 4DHydro project
<https://4dhydro.eu/catalog/>. The precipitation benchmark dataset was obtained from the EU-FP6 project UERRA (<http://www.uerra.eu>). SSM
and surface fluxes observations are available at the ISMN and FLUXNET webpages (<https://ismn.earth/en/> and <https://fluxnet.org/>).

Author contributions. AGG wrote the original draft based on a report written by PF. PF and LB produced the precipitation results. FDP
390 produced the snow results. PS produced the soil moisture results. MO and MF produced the evapotranspiration results. All authors edited the
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